

GENERAL INFORMATION ABOUT HYDROCARBON GAS DESULFURING PROCESSES

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Hydrogen sulfide (hydrogen sulfide, hydrogen sulfide) is a colorless gas with the smell of rotten eggs and a sweetish taste. Chemical formula – H_2S . Density at standard conditions . (0 ° C, 760 mm Hg.) $\rho_{H_2S_{n.a.}} = 1.5392 \text{ g/cm}^3$. Molar mass of $M_{H_2S} = 34.082 \text{ g/mol}$. Boiling point $T_{\text{boil}} = -60.4 \text{ °C}$. Melting point $T_{\text{pl.}} = -85.60 \text{ °C}$. Critical temperature $T_{\text{cr.}} = 100 \text{ °C}$. Critical pressure – 8.82 MPa. The critical volume is $98.5 \text{ cm}^3/\text{mol}$. The critical compressibility coefficient is 0.284. The heat of vaporization at normal boiling point is 18.66 kJ/mol . The solubility of hydrogen sulfide in water at ambient conditions . is 3 rpm. Mixtures of hydrogen sulfide with air are explosive within the concentration range of H_2S (% vol.) – 4h 45.

Hydrogen sulfide is a strong nerve poison: acute poisoning occurs at a concentration of 0.2–0.3 mg/m³ , concentrations above 1 mg/m³ are lethal. Maximum permissible maximum one-time concentration of hydrogen sulfide in the air of populated areas MPCm.r. = 0.008 mg/m³ .

Hydrogen sulfide is an acid that causes chemical and electrochemical (in the presence of water) corrosion of metals. Under certain conditions, sulfide cracking of metals occurs.

The corrosive effect of gas with a content of 0.025% H_2S and above is noted; this percentage is considered the “threshold” of the corrosive concentration of hydrogen sulfide, below which the presence of H_2S is considered “traces”. However, the presence of other factors (high pressure, the presence of H_2O , O_2) can lead to corrosion even with a lower hydrogen sulfide content.

Thus, the purification of hydrocarbon gas from hydrogen sulfide is caused not only by sanitary and hygienic requirements, but is also dictated by production necessity:

- protect pipes, equipment and equipment from corrosion during transportation, processing and use of gas;
- have gas suitable for domestic, power and industrial
- use;
- obtain by processing purified gases products of proper
- condensation without admixture of sulfur compounds.

Permissible content of hydrogen sulfide in purified hydrocarbon gas according to GOST 5542-87 "Natural flammable gases for industrial and municipal purposes. Technical conditions » clause 1.1 should not exceed 0.02 g/m³.

There are a large number of methods for purifying hydrocarbon gas, which are conventionally classified into three groups - absorption, adsorption and catalytic methods (see Fig. 1.). The most widely used are the first methods, which allow any initial impurity content in the gas, and adsorption processes are used for low initial impurity contents (3–5% vol.), but at the same time they allow deep purification of the gas [1].

Absorption methods, according to the nature of the absorbent used, are divided into methods of chemical absorption (chemisorption), physical absorption, combined and oxidative.

Chemisorption processes are based on the chemical interaction of hydrogen sulfide with the active component of the absorbent, which in these processes uses amines (processes: Amin-gard (chemisorbent - alkanolamine + water), Adip (chemisorbent - diisopropanolamine + water), Economin (chemisorbent - diglycolamine + water) and alkaline solutions (processes: Benfield (chemisorbent - potassium carbonate + water + benfield additives), Catacarb (chemisorbent - potash solution + corrosion inhibitor + catalyst). Chemical absorption processes are characterized by high selectivity in relation to acidic components and allow achieving a high degree of purification from hydrogen sulfide [2].

References:

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